

Automated Interview Assessment System Based on AI-Driven Emotion and Confidence Evaluation

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Abstract

This survey paper presents a detailed exploration of the *Automated Interview Assessment System (AIAS)* designed to offer automated, real-time feedback on candidates' emotions, confidence levels, and knowledge during mock interviews. By utilizing advanced artificial intelligence algorithms, the system analyses facial expressions, voice modulations, and textual content to provide comprehensive assessments. The increasing integration of artificial intelligence into various sectors necessitates tools that can assist individuals in navigating the complex landscape of job interviews. The AIAS addresses this demand by providing objective, data-driven feedback aimed at improving interview performance. This survey discusses the evolution of AI-based interview systems, outlines the methodology of AIAS, presents experimental results, highlights the challenges encountered, and explores future prospects for improving the system.

1. Introduction

The job interview is often the most crucial aspect of any recruitment process, as it serves as a significant determinant of a candidate's suitability for a role. During interviews, candidates are evaluated on multiple fronts, including emotional composure, confidence, and subject matter knowledge. Traditionally, interviews rely heavily on human judgment, which can introduce biases or subjectivity. Such biases may arise from the interviewer's preconceived notions or emotional states, which can skew their evaluations.

To address these limitations, automated systems like AIAS are designed to provide objective, data-driven insights that can help candidates improve their performance. The rise of artificial intelligence has led to the development of tools that can assess candidates more systematically. In this paper, we examine the Automated Interview Assessment System developed to integrate AI into the mock interview process. By analysing emotional responses via facial recognition, measuring confidence through

voice patterns, and assessing knowledge through textual analysis, the system offers a comprehensive evaluation of a candidate’s interview skills.

2. Related Work

The integration of artificial intelligence into human resource management has been widely studied, particularly in automating various aspects of recruitment. Existing work in AI-based assessments has primarily focused on emotion recognition systems, like Ekman's Facial Action Coding System (FACS), which recognizes facial expressions to detect emotions. This method has proven valuable in measuring stress or anxiety levels, factors that can directly affect interview performance.

In addition to emotion recognition, significant research has been conducted in the area of speech analysis for confidence evaluation. Studies suggest that speech patterns—such as pitch, modulation, and fluency—serve as reliable indicators of a speaker's confidence. For instance, lower pitch variation and consistent fluency are generally associated with confidence, whereas irregular patterns often signify nervousness. The ability to quantify confidence through voice patterns is critical for interviews, where perceived confidence can significantly influence an interviewer’s assessment.

Finally, Natural Language Processing (NLP) has been extensively utilized to assess knowledge and the content of responses. NLP techniques can analyse the relevance, depth, and correctness of the answers provided during an interview, offering a multifaceted view of the candidate's expertise and comprehension.

<i>System Name</i>	<i>Emotion Recognition Method</i>	<i>Confidence Evaluation Method</i>	<i>Knowledge Assessment Method</i>	<i>Accuracy (%)</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Ekman’s FACS	Facial Expression Analysis	N/A	N/A	78	Effective for basic emotions
AIAS(Proposed System)	CNN-based Facial Analysis	RNN-based Voice Modulation	NLP Keyword Analysis	85	Comprehensive evaluation
Voice Analysis Tool	N/A	Pitch and Tone Analysis	N/A	82	Focus on speech patterns
NLP Interview Evaluator	N/A	N/A	Advanced NLP Techniques	87	Deep content analysis

3. Methodology

The AIAS system comprises three major modules: emotion recognition, confidence analysis, and knowledge assessment. Below is a detailed explanation of each module.

- 1. Emotion Recognition Module:** This module employs Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to analyse facial expressions captured during the interview. The system identifies micro-expressions and categorizes them into emotional states such as happiness, surprise, sadness, or anxiety. The recognition of these emotional states is critical for assessing whether a candidate can maintain composure under pressure. Training a CNN involves utilizing large datasets of facial expressions, improving accuracy as the system interacts with more diverse emotional states. The emotion recognition system can adapt over time, learning from each interaction and refining its predictive capabilities.
- 2. Confidence Evaluation Module:** Confidence is evaluated through voice modulation analysis. The system records and analyses the candidate's speech patterns, focusing on variations in pitch, tone, and fluency. Here, an RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) model is employed to track how consistent and clear the voice is over time. A stable pitch and tone generally correlate with higher confidence levels, while fluctuations may indicate nervousness. This module is particularly important as it provides insights into how well candidates can manage their anxiety during interviews, an essential skill for success in high-pressure environments.
- 3. Knowledge Assessment Module:** Using advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, this module evaluates the content of the candidate's responses. It parses the responses, checks for the use of relevant keywords, and compares the answers to a pre-defined set of correct or ideal responses. By employing techniques such as sentiment analysis and keyword extraction, the system provides a score for the depth and accuracy of knowledge demonstrated. The NLP module also has the capability to adapt to various domains, allowing it to be customized for specific job roles or industries.

Fig. 1. Architecture of System

Fig. 2. Working of CNN Algorithm

4. Experimental Results

To validate the performance of AIAS, we conducted a study involving 100 participants from various professional backgrounds. Each participant underwent a mock interview where the system evaluated their performance across the three metrics: emotion, confidence, and knowledge. Below are the key findings:

- **Emotion Recognition:** The system successfully identified emotional states with 85% accuracy. It demonstrated high accuracy in detecting stress and anxiety but occasionally struggled with more subtle emotions like confusion or mild discomfort. These results underscore the need for further refinements in the emotion recognition algorithms to enhance their sensitivity to nuanced emotional expressions.
- **Confidence Scoring:** Confidence ratings were generated based on voice patterns, with a 90% correlation to human evaluations. The system excelled in identifying nervousness through speech disruptions, pauses, and inconsistent pitch. This capability is particularly useful for helping candidates understand how their verbal communication might be perceived in a real interview setting.
- **Knowledge Assessment:** The system accurately assessed the depth of knowledge in 87% of the cases. However, it faced challenges when dealing with ambiguous or highly creative answers that did not fit neatly into the predefined knowledge framework. This highlights the importance of enhancing the NLP algorithms to better accommodate varied response types and encourage creative thinking.

Participants reported a better understanding of their strengths and weaknesses, particularly in controlling emotions and boosting confidence during interviews. They expressed appreciation for the constructive feedback provided, which allowed them to practice and improve.

Fig. 3. Scoring module

Metric	AIAS Performance (%)	Human Evaluat Performance (%)	Observations
Emotion Recognition	85	80	High accuracy in stress detection
Confidence Scoring	90	88	Strong correlation with speech patterns
Knowledge Assessment	87	85	Effective in structured responses
Overall User Satisfaction	92	N/A	Participants felt more prepared

5. Discussion

The use of AI in mock interview systems introduces a level of objectivity that is challenging to achieve with human evaluators. Emotion detection allows candidates to identify stressors that may adversely affect their performance, while confidence scoring based on speech provides a direct measure of how well candidates handle pressure. Furthermore, NLP-based knowledge assessments offer immediate

feedback on the quality of answers, allowing candidates to refine their responses in real-time.

Nevertheless, there are notable limitations. The emotion recognition system's accuracy tends to decrease under varying lighting conditions or when candidates wear facial obstructions (e.g., glasses, masks). These factors can distort facial recognition capabilities, making it essential to enhance the system's adaptability in different environments. Additionally, the voice analysis system requires further tuning to effectively handle accents or speech impediments, which may affect confidence scoring and overall evaluations.

Future work will focus on integrating more diverse datasets to improve the generalization capabilities of the AI models. The goal is to enhance the system's robustness against variations in user characteristics. Additionally, improvements to the NLP module will help it accommodate more creative or spontaneous responses that go beyond rigid, structured answers

6. Conclusion

This survey has explored the Automated Interview Assessment System and its ability to provide real-time evaluations on emotion, confidence, and knowledge. By addressing the limitations of human-based evaluations, AIAS represents a significant step forward in interview training and preparation. With continuous improvements in AI technologies, systems like AIAS could become an integral part of career development and job preparation, offering invaluable resources to candidates aiming for success in their professional journeys.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] P. Ekman, "Facial Action Coding System (FACS): The Manual," Consulting Psychologists Press, Palo Alto, CA, 2002.
- [2] Y. Lu and Y. Zhang, "Speech Emotion Recognition Using CNN and RNN Techniques," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 123, April 2019.

- [3] S. Huang and L. Wang, "Automated Knowledge Assessment in Interview Simulations Using NLP," Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Data Science and AI, pp. 45-52, 2021.
- [4] G. Schuller, "Real-Time Emotion Recognition for Interview Assessments," IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 300-309, July 2022.
- [5] J. Smith and A. Brown, "Natural Language Processing Techniques for Automated Interview Evaluation," 2023 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and NLP (CINLP), IEEE Xplore, June 2023.
- [6] M. Johnson and R. Lee, "AI-Driven Voice Analysis for Confidence Evaluation in Interviews," Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research, vol. 48, pp. 12-19, 2020.
- [7] T. Clark, "Improving Job Interview Outcomes with Emotion Detection Systems," Proceedings of the 2020 IEEE International Conference on Human-Centered Computing, IEEE Xplore, August 2020.
- [8] S. Gupta, "Challenges in Emotion Recognition Using Machine Learning Models," IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 1555-1565, May 2021.
- [9] K. Wu and J. Li, "Advanced Techniques for Real-Time Voice Confidence Analysis in Interview Simulations," Proceedings of the 2022 International Conference on Speech and Language Processing, IEEE Xplore, February 2022.
- [10] B. A. Jones, "Application of Deep Learning Models in Candidate Assessment," IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 3451-3459, March 2021.
- [11] D. Patel and S. Shah, "Automated Mock Interviews for Job Preparations Using AI-Based Emotion and Confidence Evaluation," 2024 IEEE International Conference on Educational Technologies (EDUTECH), IEEE Xplore, April 2024.